

ISic1267

I.Sicily inscription 1267

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140756

1. ἔνθα [κίτε ἢ καλῆς]
2. μνήμης [ἢ δεῖνα]
3. δούλη Χ (ριστο) [ἤ ἀγαθή],
4. ζήσασα [ἔτη —' τὸν]
5. βίον ἀνε[παύσατο νώ]-
6. ναις Σεπ[τεμβρίας].
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492874

EDCS 39101636

PHI 140756

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0442 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1267. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385719>